

Sustainable tourism development in an Alpine destination: a case study

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Introduction

A modular concept for the case study: Sustainable tourism development in an Alpine destination

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1. Case Study Introduction

The case study is developed based on a modular concept. The purpose of the case study is to provide interdisciplinary knowledge and learning exercises about tourism and sustainable development to students of different education and training levels. The entire case study can be taught including all its eight modules in one day (excluding preparation and reading). The case study is applicable to all Lucerne University of Applied Sciences and Arts department courses, where sustainability is addressed or is a relevant teaching topic.

For every use of the case study, the basic modules No.2. *Sustainability* and Nr. 3. *Destination* should be taught together with at least one elective modul (Nos. 4 to 8). All the documents relating to the case study are available for students and for lecturing and teaching staff.

The case study documents can be continuously adapted and the modules can also be taught by teaching or professional staff without needing special training to the module topics.

Basics

The basic modules consist of two documents No. 2 *Sustainability* and No. 3. *Fictitious Destination*.

Module No.2. *Sustainability*: This sub-module offers a teaching tool about sustainable tourism development. The teaching material covers all three dimensions of sustainability and contains definitions and principles of national and international relevance.

Module No.3 *Fictitious Destination*: The sub-module describes a typical Alpine destination. The destination is fictitious thus enabling it to be easily adapted for use with all other modules.

Module

Each module deals with a thematic area, which is typically relevant to an Alpine destination. Each module is structured with content that enables networked thinking in relation to sustainability issues.

The completion of each module should be possible in one or two teaching lessons (in addition to 60 minutes of preparation time during which the students can do the background reading for a module. Recommended additional reading and Internet links are also provided.

Every module has following structure:

- a) Introduction to the topic and presentation of learning objectives
- b) Explanation about the topic or the sustainable tourism issue
- c) Good practice examples from an Alpine region relevant to the case study
- d) Exercises that can be done in groups during one or two lessons
- e) A bibliography for the basic reading (the reading should not take more than 60 minutes)
- f) Up to five recommended Internet links providing additional information
- g) An extended bibliography listing additional reading, which can be used at master's level or for students in further education.

Group exercises

Each module has an exercise, which is suitable for group work during a lesson in a classroom situation. The basic idea is that every exercise promotes a new learning skill and thus, students can apply their knowledge to a relevant issue linked to a very specific development problem at the fictitious destination.

Chapter 2: Basics of Sustainability

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2. Module 2: Basics of Sustainability

Module 2: Learning objectives

- Recognise and understand the concept and the drivers of sustainable development.
- Recognise and understand the concept and the principles of sustainable tourism.
- Recognise important management tools for the implementation of the sustainable development in tourism.

2.1. Sustainable development

The concept of sustainable development is defined as “*a development that satisfies the needs of the present without risking future generations not being able to meet their own needs.*” in the much-cited Brundtland Report in 1987.

The term "sustainability" means “lasting for a long time”. Therefore, sustainable development implies a long-term concept that focuses on processes involving natural, social and economic capital. That means:

- The ecological processes make use of the natural capital (natural resources) in a way that serves all the earth’s living organisms.
- Societies should develop in such a way that they are fair and equitable for all.
- Economies should develop in such a way that opportunities and possibilities will exist for both today's and future generations.

As the three dimensions of sustainability are interrelated and cannot be separated, sustainable development is often represented by three overlapping circles (see Figure 1).

Various concepts and theories describe the meaning of sustainable development. It is considered as one of the most complex issues of our time. Sustainable development is based on ethical principles, as well as on inter- and intragenerational justice. It affects all industries, all societies and all human beings on Earth.

Figure 1: Economic, environmental and social dimensions of the society in which natural and socio-economic capital are in a continuous flow.

2.2. Drivers of sustainable development

As life on Earth has to be possible in the future, sustainable development is a compelling necessity and a logical paradigm. However, critics consider the concept as too idealistic and its implementation as impossible.

One of the main reasons why most societies have committed to sustainable development is the different challenges and problems encountered in nature and by people. Such issues can not be resolved without adapting human development patterns.

Most sustainability problems are globally relevant, affect all societies and their environments. All sustainability issues have an economic, social and environmental dimension which are always linked (Figure1).

Sustainability is linked to the following main issues:

A) A growing population increases the need for natural capital / natural resources, which are limited (we have only one Earth).

(B) Socio-economic impacts of human activity and the increased utilization of resources lead to problems such as a loss of biodiversity and cultural heritage through human activities such as mining, deforestation, fishing, agriculture and other activities that exploit existing resources. The resultant numerous negative and harmful effects of these activities include, pollution, waste and altered landscapes. These in turn influence the economy as well as people's quality of life. Table 1 summarises some common sustainability themes.

Table 1: Common sustainability themes

Economy	Society	Environment
Wealth inequality	Fairness at work	Global warming & climate change
Unfair treatment of employees	Gender equality in organisations	Biodiversity loss
	Respect for minorities	Altered landscapes
	Accessibility	Waste and pollution
	Impact of tourism on local communities	Deforestation
	Interactions between locals and tourists at destinations	Reduced ecosystem services
	Loss of civil rights	
	Loss of shareholdings	
	Loss of cultural heritage	
	Corruption	

The question of responsibility is a central aspect to sustainable development principles. Sustainability is, in principle, the responsibility of the whole of society including the Government, private sector companies, non-profit organisations, as well as individual consumers. Sustainability is a process in which the question of responsibility for today's problems and the shaping of future is key.

“Corporate Social Responsibility” (CSR) is often mentioned and is used interchangeably in the context of sustainability. While sustainable development encompasses all the responsibility towards the planet and its peoples, CSR relates to companies and their voluntary actions to implement responsibility within their organisations to achieve sustainable development goals (Bassen et al., 2005, 234)¹.

2.3. Sustainable Tourism

The concept of sustainable development is also applied to tourism. Currently, the UNWTO defines sustainable tourism as "*tourism that takes full account of its current and future economic, social and environmental impacts, addressing the needs of visitors, the industry, the environment and host communities*".

This definition is applicable to all forms of tourism in all types of destinations, including mass tourism and the various segments of niche tourism.

Sustainability principles refer to the environmental, economic, and socio-cultural aspects of tourism development, and a suitable balance must be established between these three dimensions to achieve long-term sustainability.

¹ Bassen, A., Jastram, S. und Meyer, K. (2005). Corporate Social Responsibility: Eine Begriffserklärung. Zeitschrift für Wirtschafts- und Unternehmensethik: 6/2, Rainer Hamp Verlag, 231-236

The Global Sustainable Tourism Council's criteria for sustainable tourism focusses on social and environmental responsibility, as well as the positive and negative economic and cultural impacts of tourism. The criteria are organized into the following four topics.

- A. Sustainable management
- B. Socioeconomic impacts
- C. Cultural impacts
- D. Environmental impacts (including consumption of resources, reducing pollution, and conserving biodiversity and landscapes)

2.4. Principles of sustainable tourism

The three most important principles of sustainable tourism are:

- 1) Make optimal use of environmental resources that constitute a key element in tourism development, maintaining essential ecological processes and helping to conserve natural heritage and biodiversity;
- 2) Respect the socio-cultural authenticity of host communities, conserve their established, living cultural heritage and traditional values, and contribute to inter-cultural understanding and tolerance;
- 3) Ensure viable, long-term economic operations, providing fairly distributed socio-economic benefits to all stakeholders, including stable employment and income-earning opportunities and social services to host communities, and contributing to poverty alleviation.

Sustainable tourism development requires an informed participation of all relevant stakeholders, as well as strong political leadership to ensure wide participation and consensus building. Achieving sustainable tourism is a continuous process and requires the constant monitoring of its impacts, as well as introducing the necessary preventive and/or corrective measures whenever necessary.

Sustainable tourism should also maintain a high level of tourist satisfaction and ensure a meaningful experience to the tourists, raising their awareness about sustainability issues and promoting sustainable tourism practices amongst them.

2.5. Management instruments for implementation

There are many tools for the tourism industry to help sector-wide development towards sustainability. These include:

- laws and regulations
- policy goals and frameworks
- strategy and planning tools
- codes and standards
- voluntary measures such as certifications

To achieve sustainability in tourism, all stakeholders in the sector must work together towards a shared vision of sustainable development in a continuous improvement process. Success can only be achieved if the sector:

- takes account of its full economic, social and environmental impacts;
- measures and monitors relevant tourism impacts using relevant indicators;
- adjusts management processes to improve the negative impacts of tourism and facilitate more positive impacts instead;

- communicates the management progress achieved towards sustainable tourism;
- reviews sustainable tourism vision and goals regularly and involves relevant stakeholders in the continuous improvement of the sector: that means businesses and the destination together as one entity.

Reading:

Heinrich, H. und Michelsen, G. (2014). Nachhaltigkeitswissenschaften. Springer Verlag. 1-59.

Global Sustainable Tourism Criteria: <http://www.gstcouncil.org/sustainable-tourism-gstc-criteria/criteria-for-destinations.html>

2.6. Additional References:

Bundesamt für Raumentwicklung ARE (2012). Tourismus und nachhaltige Entwicklung, gute Beispiele und Aktionsmöglichkeiten. p. 9-13

Wehrli, R. Weber, F., Stettler, J. und Taufer, B. (2013). Herausforderungen eines Nachhaltigkeitsmanagement in Tourismusdestinationen. Zeitschrift für Tourismuswissenschaft 1, 41-55.

Chapter 3: A typical Swiss Alpine destination

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3. Module 3: «A typical Swiss alpine destination»

Module 3: Learning objectives

All students have the background information about the destination and can create an image of the destination. The Module 3. “Destination” serves as a preparation for all lessons (requires about 20 minutes reading time).

Modules 4-8 have specific exercises that can be used during lessons with the aid of the “Destination” module.

3.1. Latest news from Schoenblick:

Chinese investor plans tourism resort in Schoenblick

A Chinese investor wants to build an exclusive tourist resort in the municipality of Schoenblick. The planned investments amount to 98 million Swiss Francs.

Today the president of the municipality of Schoenblick informed the population about the planned resort. The investor from China plans to build a 4-star-premium holiday resort village that will include 35 buildings with a total of 250 rooms, 3 restaurants, various shops, a wellness area and an outdoor swimming pool for around CHF 98 million on an area of around 35,000 square meters. The resort is designed specifically for guests from the emerging markets of Brazil, India, Russia and China (BRIC).

The construction period for the resort will be around three to four years. After completion, the resort village will be sold to a hotel investor, who will hire an operator. According to calculations, a profitable management of the plants will be achieved after three years of operation, provided that an occupancy rate of 51% on a yearly average and later of at least 69% is achieved.

It is still unclear exactly where the resort will be built. At the moment, there are still a number of localities under consideration for selection, all of which have their advantages and disadvantages. For some, the construction of the resort project and the resort village would require the elimination of a special use zone. In other words, the proposed zone would have to be redesignated for the purposes of the resort. Various municipal council experts will be called upon to make the necessary inquiries.

The proponents of the project hope that a tourism boost to the municipality of Schoenblick will result from the resort village's presence and will also provide additional jobs, generate tax income and income for local trades people resulting from orders.

The opponents fear that the resort will create a large number of «cold beds» in Schoenblick - beds in apartments that are unused for much of the year. There are also concerns about the resort's target group and the fact that foreign companies and / or personnel may be preferred to build and operate the resort. In addition, the opponents are particularly concerned about possible rezoning required to accommodate the construction project.

Now, the task of the local community is to tender a submission to the municipality. A preliminary assessment will be completed in three months.

3.2. Background information about the Alpine destination Schoenblick

Schoenblick is situated in the southern part of Switzerland at 1'100 meters above sea level. It is a typical European Alpine destination. Schoenblick is a somewhat secluded, but is nevertheless easily accessible via a well-connected road system (Kantonsstrasse), as well as by public transport (train). The nearest big town is Chur, which is located approximately 40 km away. Zurich airport is approximately 150 km from Schoenblick.

The village of Schoenblick has about 2,800 inhabitants, who live in the village all year round (see Table 2). The seasonal fluctuation of the number of inhabitants and tourists is due to the number of second home occupants and high number tourists visiting (over four seasons). The most important economic sector in Schoenblick is tourism and responsible for employment in all sectors (Table 2).

Table 2 Community profile of Schoenblick

Population		
Residents	2013	2,845
Population density per km ²	2013	19.9
Change in %	2012-2013	0.7
Through migration	2012-2013	0.4
Through natural increase	2012-2013	0.3
Foreign nationals in %	2013	18.2
Age distribution in %		
0-19 years	2013	15.2
20-64 years	2013	68.1
>64 years	2013	16.7
Area		
Area in km ²	2013	79.3
Settlement area in %	2013	57.9
Agricultural area in %	2013	15.7
Forests and copses in %	2013	25.5
Non-productive areas in %	2013	1.9
Economy		
Employed total	2013	1,655
Primary sector	2013	112
Secondary sector	2013	423
Tertiary sector	2013	1,120
Businesses establishments total	2013	288
Primary sector	2013	35
Secondary sector	2013	38
Tertiary sector	2013	215
Housing		
New housing units per 1000 residents	2013	6.7
Rate of vacant housing units	2013	0.18
Social security		
Social assistance rate	2013	0.35

Figure 2: Pictures from Schoenblick in Summer and Winter

Source: myswitzerland.com

Source: myswitzerland.com

3.3. History of tourism in Schoenblick

Historically, Schoenblick developed as a summer destination, where outdoor activities as well as wellness and health played an important role. The reason for its development as a tourist destination was the improvement of railways in 1923. Six years later a road for cars was opened.

In 1933, the first ski-lift was built for ski-tourism. At the same time numerous new hotels were established in addition to the existing health resorts. In 1950, the aerial tramway with nice views of the beautiful Horn (1972 m above sea level) was opened.

Over time, Schoenblick has promoted the many natural attractions, cultural attractions and activities available to guests visiting. Today, Schoenblick is a successful and very well-known all year-round sports and holiday destination and it is also an integral part of various regional cooperations (e.g. regional ski association).

Schoenblick is a year-round destination although visitor numbers fluctuate due to various economic factors (a strong Swiss Franc, attractive prices and offers at nearby destinations in Austria and Italy). The statistics of the Schoenblick Cablecar company show, for example, that about 87,000 visitors were registered in summer 2013. This corresponds to a decrease of 4'350 visitors (-5%) compared to 2012. The same trend emerges for the winter season 2012/2013, with 322,000 visitors counted a decrease of 11.2% compared to the 2011/2012 season. The hotel statistics show similar trends (see Table 4 and Figure 4).

3.4. Tourism- and leisure facilities and experiences

The accommodation industry consists of 35 companies in all categories (with a focus on 3 *** hotels) with a total of 2'317 beds. In addition there are about 2'000 beds in apartments and group accommodation. Schoenblick has a diverse tourism and leisure infrastructure. It is very well known as a ski and hiking region with a total of more than 180 km of ski and snowboard slopes and over 400 kilometers of marked hiking and themed trails.

In Schoenblick you will find 25 restaurants and cafés, various bars and clubs, as well as a seminar and conference center, a rope park, a camping ground and other attractions such as a small regional museum. The winter and summer activities available in Schoenblick are listed below.

Activities in winter season

Activities in summer season

Source Piktoprogramme: Fotolia

Figure 3 Activities in winter and summer season

Figure 4: Seasonal development of overnight stays in Schoenblick from 2011-2013

Source: Schoenblick Tourismusstatistik 2013

3.5. Energy and Resources

Within two years, the municipality of Schoenblick would like to be able to identify itself with the label «Energy city». This energy certificate is a proof of performance for municipalities that present and implement a sustainable municipal energy policy. Energy parks promote renewable energies, environmentally compatible mobility and rely on the efficient use of resources. In connection with this project, the energy concept 2015 to 2018 of the municipality of Schoenblick provides for the promotion of photovoltaic systems. Appropriate locations are to be given financial support when investing in appropriate facilities. The municipal council wants to promote renewable energies.

Table 5 shows the share of the various means of transport on arrival:

Table 5: Arrivals means of transport

Means of transport	Percentage %	Comments
Flights	35%	Flight till Zürich, Basel or Genf
Railways	15%	
Car	43%	
Bus	7%	

Table 6 shows an overview of how the majority of guests arrive from the various markets of origin. On site, the tourists travel on foot, by local bus or in their own cars..

Table 6: Primary usage of transportation to arrivals market

Market	Arrival and departure per	Average km for Arrivals and Departures
Switzerland	Car	260 km
Germany	Car	1'300 km
United Kingdom (UK)	Flight	2'000 km
Rest of Europe	Car	1'600 km
USA	Flight	14'000 km
China	Flight	18'000 km
India	Flight	16'000 km
Brazil	Flight	22'000 km
Russia	Flight	10'000 km
Others	Flight	15'000 km

3.6. Landscape and landscape protection in Schoenblick

As a destination, Schoenblick has many special qualities. It is a compact settlement and has no scattered developments. Within the municipal area of Schoenblick, there are both municipal nature protection zones and landscape protection zones. Building construction is banned in the nature protection zones. In the landscape protection zones the existing appearance of the area has to be maintained. Buildings and landscaping have to be suitably designed using appropriate materials and colors to fit in with the local landscape. In Schoenblick, there are currently no specific measures regarding the protection of biodiversity. Figure 5 shows the zonal plan of Schoenblick.

Figure 5: Zone plan of Schoenblick

Source: Federal Office for Land Survey

Legend of the zone plan

Touristische Zonen und Freizeitzonen	Ortsbild- und Kulturgüterschutzzonen	Gefahrenzonen
Wintersportzone	Freihaltezone	Gefahrenzone 1
Zone für Sport- und Freizeitnutzungen	Ortsbildschutzzone	Gefahrenzone 2
Campingzone	Übrige Ortsbildschutzzone	keine GFZ innerh. EB gem. Richtlinie 6.5.97
Übrige Zone Tourismus und Freizeit	Archäologiezone	keine GFZ innerhalb EB
	Archäologische Schutzzone	von Regierung/Departement nicht genehmigte Z...
	Übrige Kulturgüterschutzzone	
Natur- und Landschaftsschutzzonen	Grundnutzungszonen	
Naturschutzzone	Zentrumszone/Kernzone	Wohnzone A/1
Landschaftsschutzzone	Dorfkernzone	Wohnzone B/2
Ruhezone	Übrige Zentrumszone	Wohnzone C/3
Wald- und Wildschutzzone	Dorfzone	Wohnzone D/4
Weitere Natur- und Landschaftsschutzzone	Dorferweiterungszone	Übrige Wohnzone
Trockenstandortzone A	Kernerweiterungszone	Wohnmischzone
Trockenstandortzone B	Übrige Erweiterungszone	
Kulturlandschaftszone		
Zone geschützte Moorlandschaften	Zone für touristische Einrichtungen	Übrige Zonen für Verkehrsanlagen
Gewerbemischzone	Zone für Sportbauten und Sportanlagen	Zone für Sport- und Freizeitnutzungen
Gewerbezone	Zone für öffentliche Bauten und Anlagen	Golfplatzzone
Industriezone	Zone für öffentliche Bauten	Campingzone
Lagerzone	Zone für öffentliche Anlagen	Übrige Zone Tourismus und Freizeit
Materialumschlagszone	Zone für Kleinbauten und Nebenanlagen	
Hotelzone		
Kurzzone		
Forstwirtschaftszone	Landwirtschaftszone	
Wald	Intensivlandwirtschaftszone	
Übrige forstwirtschaftliche Nutzungszonen	Naturschutzzone	
Freihaltezone		

3.7. Local population

The inhabitants of Schoenblick are involved with numerous sports and cultural associations which are popular meeting points for all residents. Furthermore, the traditional customs are actively practiced and the longstanding locals like to keep to themselves. The newly arrived Swiss residents, as well as the foreign population tend to mix with their own at their cultural clubs. So far, the local population has hardly been involved with the tourism development of Schoenblick and they desire to have more opportunities for learning languages. Schoenblick has a library and a toy library for the residents. Youth meetings, which are aimed at youths aged between 13 and 18 are directed by a youth worker.

3.8. Culture

In the village of Schoenblick, local culture stills plays a major role. The small castle "Schoenblick" is located on the top of a hill. Guided tours are available on request. The buildings can also be rented for special and private events. The village of Schoenblick is also registered in the ISOS (Federal Inventory of Protected Sites of National Importance). In particular, the Schoenblick village centre contributes to this characteristic Alpine location.

Intangible cultural heritage can still be found in Schoenblick. However, many traditions are slowly being lost or practiced only by a few locals. For example, the local dialect is increasingly being mixed with the dialects of the new arrivals. In addition, the local music style and the traditional handicraft techniques e.g. the carvings are increasingly subject to external influences. Traditional customs that are still of great importance, are the Alpine trip which takes place annually in September and the farmersmarket, an important attraction for many locals. Whilst the winter carnival traditions continue to be encouraged, other traditions linked to festivals are becoming less important.

Chapter 4: Sustainable Tourism Policy

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4. Module 4: Sustainable Tourism Policy

The aim of this case study is to impart knowledge about tourism and sustainable development in an interdisciplinary way. The case study consists of different modules. The basic module consists of two documents:

- Sustainability: This module introduces the topic of sustainable tourism development in an Alpine destination.
- Fictitious Destination: The second module describes a typical alpine destination.

This is followed by several modules dealing with a field of action typical for an alpine destination: politics, society, energy, culture and landscape.

To work on this module, you must have studied the two basic modules.

Module 4: Learning objectives

- Distinguish the importance of policy compared to the importance of action plans in the medium to long term development of a small destination.
- Differentiate international, national and regional tourism policy measures, which are relevant for a small Swiss Alpine destination.
- Identify key policy areas relevant to the management of a tourist destination in accordance with the objectives of sustainable tourism.
- Develop capabilities to formulate a vision and strategic objectives for a destination that will help it develop according to sustainability principles.

Tourism policy

Tourism policy is the sum of all measures taken by public and private-law institutions at all political levels, which directly and indirectly, consciously or unconsciously determine the design and development of tourism (Mundt, 2004). The aim of tourism policy is to ensure optimal conditions for the tourism industry, in particular its long-term sustainable development. Tourism policy is usually defined at national or regional levels and includes specific strategic documents and operational action plans for implementation. In Switzerland, the main goal of tourism policy is to increase the competitiveness of Switzerland as a sustainable growth industry destination.

Direct tourism policy includes all measures which are exclusively based on or directly related to tourism. For example: credit to a hotel, tourism advertising, tourist training and education, cooperation with international organizations.

Indirect tourism policy includes measures that do not have an impact on tourism, but that do have a significant impact on the industry. For example: land use planning, environmental policy, transport policy, various non-tourism laws, foreign policy.

Twelve policy areas have been defined internationally in the area of sustainable tourism, that must be addressed in all three dimensions of sustainable development (see Table 1).

4.1. Objectives and measures

In principle, the following must be taken into account when formulating guidelines and objectives and implementing measures:

- (a) The government and the tourism industry must define specific strategies and measures to achieve the formulated policies. In many cases, measures are taken by the private sector. The role of the government is to develop and implement a setting that is conducive to industry working in an appropriate manner and working towards achieving sustainable development.
- (b) The principles must be adapted to local circumstances, e.g. for an Alpine destination.
- (c) All policies relate to the overall performance and impact of tourism and are therefore areas of interest to both national and regional authorities.

Table 7: International political goals of a sustainable destination

Policy area	What does this mean for destination management?
Economic viability	Ensuring the viability and competitiveness of tourism destinations and enterprises, so that they are able to continue to prosper and deliver benefits in the long term
Local prosperity	Maximising the contribution of tourism to the economic prosperity of the host destination, including the proportion of visitor spending that can be retained locally (that is to minimise leakages).
Employment quality	Strengthening the number and quality of local workplaces supported or created by tourism, including the level of pay, working conditions, accessibility for all without discrimination by gender, race, disability or in other ways.

Social equity	Achieving a broad and equitable distribution of the economic and social benefits of tourism to local stakeholders, including improving opportunities, income and services available to the poor.
Visitor fulfillment	Providing a safe, satisfying and fulfilling experience accessible to all visitors, without discrimination by gender, race, disability or in other ways.
Local control	Engaging and empowering the local communities in planning and decision making about the management and future development of tourism in their region, in coordination with other stakeholders.
Welfare of the community	Maintaining and strengthening the quality of life in local communities, including social structures and access to resources, facilities and livelihoods, and avoiding any form of social deprivation or exploitation.
Cultural wealth	Respecting and enhancing the historical heritage, the authentic culture, the traditions and distinctiveness of the host communities.
Integrity	Maintaining and enhancing the urban and rural landscape quality, avoiding the physical and visual degradation of the environment.
Biodiversity	Supporting the conservation of natural areas, habitats and wildlife, and minimizing damage to them.
Resource efficiency	Minimizing the use of scarce and unsustainable resources in the development and operation of tourism infrastructures and services.
Clean environment	Minimizing air, water and soil pollution as well as waste generation by tourism companies and visitors.

Source: UNWTO-UNEP, 2005

4.2. Role and tasks of the different organisations and their influence on policy affecting Swiss Alpine destinations

In principle, the role and task of tourism policy makers include:

- Controlling and monitoring activities relating to tourism, including setting rules and regulations;
- Supporting or promote tourism (for example: by creating tax benefits or additional taxation);
- Contributing financially to tourism projects (for example: to innovation ideas);
- Promoting various voluntary initiatives such as certifications and standards offered by organisations such as «fair trade» or quality labels.

Table 8: Levels of tourism policy in Switzerland

Organisation	Task/Role	Specific policy guidelines and strategies
State Secretariat for Economic Affairs (SECO) Tourism Department	The organisation is the central office for tourism within the Swiss Federal Administration. The Tourism Department is the centre of competence whose tasks include: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Monitor tourism as a trade sector - Promote tourism as a part of regional development - Act as a supervisory authority over the promotion body «Switzerland Tourism» - Represent Switzerland's tourism sector in intergovernmental organizations 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Growth strategy for Switzerland as a tourist destination: implementation program 2012-2015 (see Appendix) - New Regional Policy (NRP) <p>Link: http://www.seco.admin.ch/themen/</p>
Federal Office for Spatial Development (ARE)	The organisation deals with the following topics relevant to tourism: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Spatial development - Examination and approval of the tourism-relevant Cantonal guidelines - Transport policy (general and leisure traffic) - Strategies in the area of sustainable development - Transport policy (co-ordination office) - Agglomeration policy (Aggloprogramme) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Planning laws - Strategic and indicative plans - The Alpine Convention (1995) - Document: Tourism and Sustainable development. Good Examples and opportunities (Appendix) <p>Link: http://www.are.admin.ch/themen/</p>
Federal Office for the Environment (FOEN)	In addition to environmental policy, which is relevant to tourism, this organisation deals with a wide range of topics related to leisure, sports and tourism activities: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Sports and tourism - Sports in nature - Events - Leisure mobility - Natural tourism - Parks 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Nature and Home Protection Act (NHG) - Ordinance on the Federal Inventory of Landscapes and Natural History (VBLN) - Park regulations (PäV) / National Parks Act - Environmental Protection Act (USG) - Environmental Impact Assessment (e.g. for events) <p>Link: http://www.bafu.admin.ch</p>
Federal Office for Agriculture (FOAG)	The main tasks of the organisation include: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Protection of agriculture and natural resources - Protection of the cultivated land 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Biodiversity Action Plan - Water management and water protection

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Promotion of biodiversity - Support for agrotourism - Rural development 	Link: http://www.blw.admin.ch/
Federal Roads Office (FEDRO)	<p>The Swiss Federal Roads Office deals with, among other things, the following areas linked to tourism:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Road safety - Heavy vehicle - Planning the national roads - Road financing - Sustainable mobility 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Federal Law on Footpaths and Hiking Trails (FWG) - Ordinance on Footpaths and Hiking Trails (FWV) <p>Link: http://www.astra.admin.ch/themen/</p>
Federal Office of Transport (FOT)	<p>The organisation is committed to efficient, environmentally-friendly, safe and attractive public transport that encompasses:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Railways - Cableways - Trolleybuses - Buses - Ships 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Cableway Act and Regulation (SebG / SebV) - Railways Act (EBG) - National shipping legislation <p>Link: https://www.bav.admin.ch/bav/en/home.html</p>
Federal Office of Civil Aviation (FOCA)	<p>The organisation is responsible for the development of aviation, as well as the regulation and supervision of civil aviation.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Federal Law and Ordinance on Civil Aviation (FOCA) <p>Link: http://www.bazl.admin.ch/themen/</p>
Switzerland Tourism	<p>Switzerland Tourism is the national marketing organization commissioned by the Confederation to implement national advertising and promotion that includes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Development of marketing programs to stimulate demand - Implementation of programs on international markets - Support of the web-site myswitzerland.com - Information about the tourist offers - Market Research - Use or create advertising-relevant events and support the media - Support for tourism providers in the distribution and market processing 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The legal basis for this contract is the Federal Law and the Ordinance on the Swiss Transport Centre (Switzerland Tourismus). <p>Link: http://www.stnet.ch/de.cfm/ueber_uns/</p>
Swiss company for hotel credit (SGH)	<p>The organisation grants loans under special conditions for the renewal, new construction or acquisition of accommodation and other spa facilities. The SGH comes under the supervision of the Federal Council.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Federal Law on the Promotion of the Accommodation Industry <p>Link: http://www.sgh.ch/</p>
Swiss Federal Railways (SBB) and Post-auto Switzerland	<p>SBB and <i>Postauto</i> Switzerland have an extensive distribution network, as well as a number of tourism-relevant services.</p>	<p>Link: http://www.sbb.ch/home.html http://www.postauto.ch/</p>
Swiss Tourism Association (STV)	<p>The STV is the umbrella tourism association in Switzerland. It represents the interests of tourism providers in politics, public authorities and the public. Its main tasks are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Safeguarding the interests of the tourism industry 	<p>STV quality labels:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Quality Program «Q» - Families welcome

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Participating in all tourism policy decisions (tourism policy umbrella organization) - Information and consulting activities in the field of product design (quality improvement) - Information and co-ordination activities in the field of tourism training - Providing assistance in tourist planning 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Classification for apartments - Wellness destination - EU Ecolabel
		Link: http://www.swisstourfed.ch
Hotelleriesuisse	<p>Hotelleriesuisse is the Swiss hotel industry association. Its core tasks include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Swiss hotel classification - Representation of economic interest - Promoting young talent, education and training - Legal advice - Representation of the hotel industry interests in the Social Partnership - Publication of the independent journal htr hotel renevue 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Swiss hotel classification - Hotelpower.ch (Information and solutions on the topic of energy in hotels and hotels)
		Link: http://www.hotelleriesuisse.ch
GastroSuisse	<p>GastroSuisse is the Swiss employers' association for the catering industry and it performs the following tasks:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Represents the economic interests of the restaurant industry - Maintains a dialogue with politicians, business and the public - Promotes the image of the industry and - is engaged in vocational training. 	Link: http://www.gastrosuisse.ch
Swiss travel fund (REKA)	<p>REKA is the organization for social tourism in Switzerland and aims to promote and facilitate holidays and travel especially in Switzerland. REKA is regarded as the leading landlord of holiday apartments for families and as a second-largest Swiss provider of holiday apartments, camping accommodation and hotels.</p>	Link: http://www.reka.ch/de/
Seilbahnen Schweiz	<p>Seilbahnen Schweiz (SBS) is the association of the Swiss cable railway industry. Its purpose is to represent the common concerns and interests of SBS members and to promote their co-operation. SBS has a broad scope of activities, ranging from representation to authorities, member counselling and public relations.</p>	Link: http://www.seilbahnen.org
Canton / Region	<p>Tourism policy concerns are exercised at the Cantonal level by existing departmental and administration bodies. They are special offices or departments for tourism (for example in Graubünden). One of the most important aspects relating to tourism, concerns strategic regional planning and spatial planning.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - New Regional Policy - Cantonal spatial planning - Possibly. Cantonal tourism strategy - Strategies for regional development - Further laws and strategies in the area of law, finance, environment and energy, which affect companies and organizations
Local Municipality	<p>Municipalities can also define strategies for tourism independently. Many local municipalities have special policies for tourism and may also collect taxes. One of the key influential aspects of local councils relates to granting development approvals for certain tourism constructions. Some local councils also operate tourism information services.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Usage plan (Zones) - inclusion of the population - Financial support for investment projects - mission statements

Cantonal or regional tourism associations / associations / management organizations	Cantonal and / or regional tourism organizations undertake planning and for on the spot tourism marketing.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Performance agreements with the canton / region - Performance agreements with the tourism service providers
Universities	<p>Numerous universities, technical colleges and higher technical colleges offer tourism related education and training for students, as well as research and consulting services. The following public institutions are relevant in this context:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - University of Bern, Research Center Tourism - University of St. Gallen, Institute for Systemic Management and Public Governance - Lucerne University of Applied Sciences, Institute of Tourism - University of Applied Sciences, Chur - University of Applied Sciences, Western Switzerland / Tourism, Sierre 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Bern: http://www.cred.unibe.ch/content/forschungsstelle_tourismus/index_ger.html - St. Gallen: http://www.imp.unisg.ch/de/Unsere+Themen/Tourism+und+Freizeit - Luzern: http://www.hslu.ch/itw - Chur: http://www.htwchur.ch/tourismus/uebersicht.html - Sierre: http://tourismus.hevs.ch/Studien-gang_Tourismus__Herzlich_Willkommen_23198.98.htm

4.3. Alpine Convention (1995)

The Alpine Convention is the world's first legally binding convention for the protection of a mountain region. For the first time, a mountain area was defined as a functional geographical unit across the national borders and as a cultural and economic area facing common challenges. Signatory countries to the Alpine Convention include: Germany, France, Italy, Liechtenstein, Monaco, Austria, Slovenia and Switzerland. The Alpine Convention refers to a region comprising 43 regional areas and 5800 municipalities, inhabited by around 13 million people. The objective of the Alpine Convention is the protection and sustainable development of the Alpine Space. Concrete measures for the implementation of the objectives of the Alpine Convention can be found in the implementation protocols on the subject areas. The Convention mainly addresses land use. The main attraction in terms of tourism and leisure is to limit environmental activities and to reconcile tourism and leisure activities with environmental and social requirements, in particular by establishing resting zones. Switzerland has ratified the Framework Convention, but not the Implementing Protocols.

4.4. Sustainability policy in Arosa

Arosa is a Swiss Alpine village and has been showing great commitment to sustainable destination management. Table 7 sets out the implementation initiatives for sustainable tourism development goals.

Table 9: Economic implementation initiatives of sustainable tourism policy in Arosa

Economic Viability	Tourism has been an important factor for the local economy for almost 150 years in Arosa where the industry operates principally during two seasons. Tourism is an economically viable industry thanks to the diversified product and service range in Arosa that includes its Alpine location, numerous indoor and outdoor sports and leisure attractions, as well as diversified cultural and natural attractions. Arosa is economically 100% dependent on tourism and offers around 7,000 beds which account for 800,000 overnight stays annually.
Local Prosperity	<p>Tourism contributes significantly to the local prosperity of Arosa. The return from tourism to the local economy is ensured by various means:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> (a) Tourism companies pay a tourist promotion fee on the basis of the classification of their company (see Tourism Act of Arosa). For example, Hotels pay CHF 0.70-1.15 per booked bed, mountain railways pay 0.4% of their turnover from passenger transport, the municipality pays a fixed rate and shops, and certain companies pay an amount based on the number of employees or seats for guests (e.g. for restaurants). (b) The municipality has enacted a tourism law whereby a certain amount is collected from certain companies per night (guest and sport tax). This law also applies to owners of chalets or second homes in Arosa. The money is then used for the direct financing of local projects, which are in the exclusive interest of the guests. Moreover, it is a transparent mechanism to generate income from tourist flows. (c) The sale of regional products in shops and at specific points, such as the dairy company <i>Sennerei Maran</i> is promoted. In particular, the accommodation companies use local products and point their guests to potential sales outlets. (d) In order to promote sustainable development specifically, Arosa Tourism has created an eco-fund. Through the receipts in the "kurvensicher.ch" project and

	<p>the "Schneespass mit guter Gewissen" package (valid for use later).</p> <p>(e) Arosa Tourism has also created a local development fund for better management of the destination (Arosa location promotion).</p> <p>(f) A further initiative "Kurven-Patenschaft" (kurvensicher.ch) was recently launched. In this project, each person can sponsor a certain road curve between Chur and Arosa. On an online platform, all of the 360 roadcurves can be viewed and selected. The revenue from the initiative also flows into the eco-fund.</p>
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Source: www.arosa.ch

Table 10: Social aspects of sustainable tourism policy in Arosa

Employment Quality	<p>Arosa's tourism industry creates about 1,400 jobs in various areas, from kitchen to cleaning jobs and business management to technical work. Arosa also has a special fund "The Arosa Young Talent Promotion" for training young people, which is coordinated by Arosa Tourism. In addition, Arosa supports the younger generation of the town by providing numerous cultural, sporting and social activities.</p>
Social Equity	<p>Arosa has accommodation for every budget and any preference (from camping to five-star hotels). The destination has developed an "Arosa all-inclusive Card", which offers free access to leisure activities for all overnight guests in the summer (mid-June to mid-October). The card includes the following services: Gondola lift Hörnli-Express, Arosa-Weisshorn cable car, Urdenbahn aerial cable car, local bus, Rhätische Bahn (Arosa-Langwies-Arosa route), rope park, pedalo and boats on the Obersee lake and admission to the Schanfigger Heimatmuseum.</p> <p>Many local helpers are involved in big events. For example during the "Arosa Classic Car Race" catering is provided by chefs from Arosa..</p>
Visitor Fulfillment	<p>Arosa has a very diverse tourism product range, throughout the seasons, for all ages, budgets and interests . Arosa stands out with its "Q1" label awarded by the Swiss Tourism Association (STV). Furthermore, Arosa is one of the 23 family-friendly destinations (means all families are welcome) and one of the few members of the Swiss Alpine Pearl Network. Numerous local initiatives honour guests for their commitment to sustainable tourism. For example, those who arrive by train with the "Snow pass with good conscience" package will receive a voucher for the Arosa Comedy Festival from Arosa Tourism. Guest satisfaction surveys carried out by the Arosa Mountain Railways, indicate that the needs of the guests are largely fulfilled.</p>
Local control	<p>Since tourism is largely managed locally at the municipal level, income losses are limited and lead to positive contributions for locals. With the exception of a few companies, all companies are local or at least Swiss owned. Losses of income from the municipality of Arosa are partly limited by direct tax revenues from tourism and tourism related companies (made possible by the local Tourism Act). The eco-fund is also managed by the local tourism organization and supports local projects. In 2009, Arosa was awarded the Swiss Association for Location Management Award and in 2014 for the co-operation with the ski resort Lenzerheide.</p>
Community well-being	<p>Arosa offers a wide range of tourism products, which also promote and support many local leisure activities in a social, sports or cultural context.</p>

Cultural Richness	Arosa is increasingly known for its festivals and numerous cultural activities throughout the year. International artists from the world of comedy, classical music and opera guarantee a high standard of festivals. Arosa also has a local museum (Schanfigger Heimatmuseum), which gives visitors insight into the history of the region. The museum also has exhibits of old sports equipment and advertising posters from the early 20th century.
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Table 11: Ecological aspects of sustainable tourism policy in Arosa

Biological Diversity	Sustainability and climate protection generally play an important role for the municipality and for many tourism companies in Arosa. The destination continually invests in projects to ensure the protection of the local biophysical environment. Arosa also offers an environmentally-friendly winter holiday package "Schneespass mit guter Gewissen" (Snow pass with good conscience), in which the tourism organisation pays a contribution to the eco-fund (in principle as a compensation for CO ₂ emissions for travel and stay). So guests do not incur this additional cost. The offer includes free train travel for visitor travelling from Chur to Arosa. The «Arosa Classic Car Race» also pays an amount to the eco-fund. Arosa Tourism encourages tourists to practice sustainable tourism by providing the organisation with tips for conscious travel, such as: «Leave your car in the garage for once, and enjoy your holidays « gently mobile ».»
Environmental Purity	A natural experience and bear park is to be created in Arosa. It will be partially funded by the eco-fund and will offer summer guests a wonderful opportunity to experience and learn about the animals and natural environment they inhabit. It is anticipated that this will help raise awareness of the need for conservation of this area's biological heritage.
Resource Efficiency	The Destination of Arosa encourages all companies and guests to achieve resource efficiency. Numerous projects in this context have been financed through the eco-fund. Examples include: the financing of a new heating concept at the Arosa Comedy Festival (2008); the creation of an energy efficiency concept for the renovation of the skating rink in the Sports and Conference Center (2012). In addition, some hotels have already installed solar modules on the roof (for example the Hotel Blatter's Bellavista). With the <i>Energy Efficiency Check Initiative</i> , Arosa is conducting energy checks of tour operators to identify and label farms as a "climate friendly company Arosa" (some of the costs of analysis are financed by the eco-fund). To date, five tourism companies have participated, but many companies are implementing their own sustainability measures (e.g. Hotel Sunstar Parkhotel, Blatters Bellavista (Solar System), Electro MM (solar system), Hotel Hohe Promenade (hot water preparation). During the Winter 2013/2014 guests were able to see how much energy they could generate when moving along the «Energy Carpet» in the Valley Station <i>Weisshornbahn</i> . This device can be used to increase the awareness of alternative energy sources.
Cleaner environment	During the Winter of 2013/2014 time was allocated to education and training. For example, efficient and eco sensitive training for snowmobile drivers. Arosa also promotes the use of e-bikes for exploring the area, as well as using electric cars to drive to Arosa (charging stations are available).

Source: www.arosa.ch

Exercise in class:

Part 1) work for the next 1-2 Lessons in groups (typically 3 to 4 people per group)

Bachelor- Level:

Based on the readings about international and national tourism policy of sustainable development:

- (a) Define the difference between policy and strategy in terms of sustainable tourism.
- (b) Develop a vision for the fictitious Alpine destination, which could be adopted by all stakeholders.
- (c) Identify at least five clear objectives adopted by the relevant actors of the fictitious destination to help continue the vision of sustainable tourism..

Master- or Further education level:

Use the policy objectives in Table 7 and develop a clear vision or sustainable tourism policy for Arosa in a specific context (e.g. social cohesion).

Part 2) The students present their results to the whole group (45 minutes recommended).

Reading for the lecture:

SECO/InnoTour (2010). Schwerpunkt: Wachstumsorientierte Tourismuspolitik. Insight Nr. 5, Winter 2010. S. 1 - 6

ARE (2012). Tourismus und Nachhaltige Entwicklung. Gute Beispiele und Aktionsmöglichkeiten. Bern: ARE, S. 9 - 27

4.5. Further reading:

Alpine Convention (2005): PROTOCOL on the implementation of the Alpine Convention of 1991 in the field of tourism Official Journal of the European Union. L 337/43

Gemeinde Arosa (2004) Tourismusgesetz der Gemeinde Arosa. Fassung gemäss Urnenabstimmung von 26. September, 2004. 17 Seiten.

Further internet sources:

Arosa Gemeinde & Tourismus: www.arosa.ch

Alpine Pearls <http://www.alpine-pearls.com/en/about-us.html>

4.6. Bibliography (Theory part)

UNWTO-UNEP (2005) Making Tourism More Sustainable: A Guide for Policy Makers. UNWTO-UNEP. Madrid.

Schweizer Nachhaltigkeits-Charta für Tourismus

Mundt, J.W. (2004). Tourismuspolitik. München/Wien: Oldenbourg.

Müller, H. (2011). Tourismuspolitik. Wege zu einer nachhaltigen Entwicklung. Glarus/Chur: Rüegger.

Chapter 5: Society, Focus on local people

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5. Module 5: Society, with a focus on the local population

5.1. Introduction

Before completing this module students should have read the following texts:

- Thiem, Marion (2001). Tourismus und kulturelle Identität. In Politik und Zeitgeschichte. B47/2001 S. 27 - 31
- Bachleitner, Reinhard (2001). Alpentourismus: Bewertung und Wandel. In Politik und Zeitgeschichte B47/2001 S. 20 – 26.

Module 5: Learning objectives

- Awareness of the fundamental principles of social sustainability that are important in the context of tourism.
- Gain knowledge and an understanding of the sociocultural interactions in the context of tourism.
- Understanding the impact of tourism on local populations (opportunities and challenges).
- Understanding the link between the development of a tourist destination and a local population's attitude towards a local tourism development.

5.2. Introduction Social Sustainability and Tourism

The basic social dimension foundations for sustainable tourism development were briefly described in the basic module "Sustainability". Why the social dimension of sustainable development is important is illustrated in the following quote:

"If sustainable development is to preserve the livelihoods and opportunities for future generations in different regions, it is assumed that humans are essential beings at the same time as subjects and objects of this policy. Therefore the necessity arises to:

- Recognise the social aspect as the basis of the sustainability triangle
- The social aspect generally, as well as its structure and organizational configuration forms strength before the relations of the axis to economics and ecology." (Drilling & Schnur 2012, S. 26).

5.3. Meeting different cultures in tourism – importance for the local population

In a tourism region, people from different cultures, in different roles meet with different expectations. Thiem (2001) describes this process in detail. A possible definition of culture can be referred to here is the one of Sutter (2002, p. 90): "culture is the collective of standards, customs, norms, values and techniques that an individual has in different social contexts, to interpret the world". Whilst travellers display their source culture (i.e. the culture of their residence or place of origin) when on holidays and this contributes to how they react, the service culture and culture of the host target region also plays a key role in how these travellers react.. According to Thiem, the culture of the source region is that which is typical of the inhabitants of a tourist destination. A holiday culture is a lifestyle, which tourists seek out when travelling. The holiday culture is dependent on the respective culture and the environment and this influences the holiday expectations of the travellers. The culture of the target region encompasses everything that is typical of the inhabitants of a tourist region as a living, economic area. Finally, the service culture includes the lifestyle followed by the local population in their role as hosts, as well as the tourism facilities set up in a region. At a tourist resort, holiday and service cultures meet, with encounters between locals and guests. During debate concerning the impact of tourism on the local population hazards are usually discussed. Whereas the opportunities offered by tourism development for the local population are hardly considered. What is still missing is a comprehensive analysis on a social and cultural level of cultural or socio-structural change through tourism. According to Aschauer & Bachleitner (2010) the "not-knowledge willingness" of the cultural, social and partly ecological aspects of the tourism industry is still recognizable.

Figure 6: Cultural encounters in the context of cultural value systems

Source: Adapted presentation from Fuchs 2004, p. 119.

5.4. Local population and tourism

In this module the focus is placed on the local population, as an important group of actors at the tourist destination. More often than not the involvement of the local population in tourism developments is negligible, yet they are greatly affected by the impact of tourism, as the following quote shows:

“Tourism is primarily regarded as an economic phenomenon. In this way, economic prosperity and optimum satisfaction of the tourists needs are given priority: the marketing idea takes the "place" habitat and understands it as a tourist product: the region, the place is a tourist company, a destination that should place its product on the market in the best possible way. From a life-world perspective, a place is not a tourist product, but a living space in which work is being done and where one can recover.” (Ferrante 1994, S.134)

Only a few scientific studies are available concerning the impact of tourism on the local population. For example, Bachleitner (2000, p. 51) states: “Often, tourism triggers a bundle of sociocultural,

socio-structural and socio-ecological changes which, in their interplay as well as their social psychological consequences, have been explored in a deficient way.”

Assessment of how tourism development affects the local population in the short, medium and long term is only ever possible for specific cases and must be based on the concrete experiences of the local people and their subjective assessments. In general it can be said:

- “The more negative impacts (negative external effects) that have to be accepted, the more critical the attitude of the affected parties towards tourism and the higher the need for communication.
- The stronger the involvement in the tourism process, the more negative external effects are accepted and fewer conflicts need to be addressed.” (Ferrante 1994, p. 11).

The subjective perceptions and evaluations of the population on the development and the role of tourism at a destination vary considerably. To this end, Bachleitner (ebd., p. 64-65) hypotheses can serve as a guide to questions for tourism impact research:

- “The more a regional social and cultural system is being comprehensively shaped by tourism, the greater the process of social outlook and cultural identity, and the more this leads to negative perceptions and interpretations of tourism.
- The higher the material costs for infrastructure provision and the lower the social and environmental (utilization) effects for the disabled, the higher the potential for rejection of tourism.
- The earlier change is made to qualitative tourism (= social, ecology and economic compatibility), the higher the tourist acceptance rate by locals.
- The greater the impact on natural resources and the immediate impact on the service sector, the higher the potential for rejection of tourism by locals.
- The greater the observable success of ecology-oriented tourism, regional policy is for tourists, the more positive the tourist attitude.”

Bachleitner's hypotheses show that the ecological, economic and social dimension of sustainable development can not be viewed separately from one another in a specific case and the complex effects of all three dimensions are mutually interrelated.

5.5. Inclusion of the local population

Sustainable development requires a social learning, search and design process. The targeted inclusion of the local population is, in addition to the fulfillment of social and cultural responsibility, indispensable to meet the demands of the social dimension of sustainable development. With the involvement of all key stakeholders such as residents, stakeholders, entrepreneurs, politicians etc., it is possible to discuss different perspectives, needs and experiences in the context of tourism development processes together with future aspects and innovative solutions, which take into account of all the three dimensions of sustainable development. Sharing processes can improve coexistence and integration at a destination. For the local population are regarded not only the old "natives", but also as recruited workers, who often come from other countries. Integration and cultural exchange are an important issue in tourist communities, and are often neglected. Basically, it is possible to distinguish between formal (legally written) and informal (non-written) participation (Lüttringhaus 2000, p. 37).

Table 12: Participants

	Formal Participation	Informal Participation
Legal status	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Existing legal foundations – Prerequisites and specifications are defined 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Complement the formal procedures – Based on a voluntary basis – There is a great deal of scope for action (form, implementation, participants) – Based on conceptual considerations
Investment opportunity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Voting and electorates 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Target groups are defined in a participation concept – Open to all interested persons, including children, young people and foreigners
Opportunities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Setting conditions are known – Rights and obligations are known 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Topics of the current or future tourism development of a destination can be discussed in tailor-made settings – All parties are looking for solutions together – Improving coexistence and intercultural communication
Risks	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Participation depends on the election behavior – Young people and foreign citizens are excluded – Little dialogue and discussion opportunities 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Consciousness and will for participation must be available to authorities and the population – Communication and transparency are important; Susceptible to misunderstandings – Participation depends on trust in authorities, as well as on material and temporal resources and language skills – Too higher access thresholds can exclude population groups

Examples of the inclusion of the local population are given in the brochure of the Federal Office for Spatial Development “Tourism and Sustainable Development”. Good examples and opportunities for action”.

The voluntary minimum standard of the Global Sustainable Tourism Criteria (GSTC)², developed at a world-widelevel under the leadership of various international organisations, together with a wide range of partners, forms the basis for the integration and participation of the local population. The cultural impact of the GSTC refers to the needs and traditions of the local and regional population. In this way, the integration of foreign workers or living together in a destination is to be actively supported and promoted. In addition, the importance of targeted inclusion of the local population is emphasized by information, participation and co-decision in tourism development.

² See: <http://www.gstcouncil.org>

5.6. Practical example of the long-term and accompanying study BESTander matt: "Sociocultural and socio-economic impact of the tourism center Andermatt"

The company Andermatt Swiss Alps (ASA) is developing a tourism resort in Andermatt as an initiative of the Egyptian investor Samih Sawiris. On an area of 1.4 million square meters, six hotels, some 490 apartments in 42 buildings, 25 private villas, a swimming pool, congress facilities and an 18-hole golf course are planned for the final expansion (Andermatt Swiss Alps, no date). In addition, the ski resort is to be modernised and expanded. According to the Sustainability Report for the Plan Adjustment of Urseren, there are no precedents which show the possible social impact of this large-scale project (Ernst Basler + Partner, 2006).

Figure 7: Planned resort in Andermatt with golf course.

Source: Andermatt Swissalps, online

Aschauer & Bachleitner (2010) point out that comprehensive analyses of cultural or socio-structural change are still missing within tourism. This is where the long-term and complementary study BESTander matt³ begins by examining the sociocultural⁴ and socio-economic changes triggered by the construction of the tourism centre in Andermatt. Between 2009 and 2020, four surveys will be conducted in Andermatt⁵. The long-term and accompanying study BESTander matt is a hands-on approach that involves the population in the development of the respective research design and in the discussion of the results. The aim of the study is to answer the question of how the respondents perceive and experience the society and socio-economic impact of the tourism centre in Andermatt⁶.

³ Overall project management: Institute for Sociocultural Development at the Lucerne University of Applied Sciences - Social Work. For detailed information see www.best-ander matt.ch

⁴ Sociocultural impacts are understood as those aspects which relate to the perception and assessment of the expected and feared or already made changes that a major tourist project triggers with regard to the individual situation of the inhabitants and the collective situation of the population at the time of the survey.

⁵ Implementation of the first partial study: 2009/2010; Implementation of the second partial study 2012/2013.

⁶ 25 people were interviewed in individual interviews. In addition, group interviews were conducted with adolescents and professionals.

5.7. Hands-on elements of the study

The study BESTander matt is based on the principles of hands-on research. This means that the question of how and in which way the inhabitants, as experts in their life-world, can participate in the research process has to be asked again and again.

Figure 8: Discussion on the results conference in Andermatt.

Source: Hochschule Luzern – Soziale Arbeit

In order to meet the requirements of hands-on research, a **public information** event was held in the study BESTander matt before the start of the partial studies, where the research design was presented and discussed with the participants. The suggestions of the participants flowed into the further development of the research design as well as the methodological approach.

The results of the first and second partial studies were presented to the population at a **results conference** and discussed in groups. In addition, the participants discussed the need for action from the results presented. On the basis of the discussion results, the research team formulated fields of action, as well as possible measures for the clients and resort managers.

5.8. Support group

A local accompanying group was set up at the beginning of the first partial study. It was made up of Andermatt inhabitants and served as a link between the population, the authorities and the research team. The accompanying group met about four times a year to discuss topics addressed by the population in connection with resort development at their moderated meetings⁷. So far, the work of the accompanying group has proved its worth and is helping to promote dialogue and mutual understanding in Andermatt.

5.9. Children participation

A children's symposium entitled "miis Andermatt - iises Andermatt"⁸ was conceived and implemented in collaboration with teachers from the 4th to the 6th grade. In addition to the discussion with Andermatt as a place of life, the children involved formulated wishes for the municipal authorities, which were collected in a wish box and presented by a children's delegation at the results conference of the second partial study of the population and handed over to a member of the municipal council.

⁷ The meetings are always moderated by the same person of the Institute for Sociocultural Development. This person is not involved in the interviews in order to avoid rogue conflicts.

⁸ That "My Andermatt - Our Andermatt".

Figure 9: Children's participation day. In groups, favorite places and less popular places of children are marked on the plans

Quelle: Hochschule Luzern – Soziale Arbeit

5.10. Conclusion

The long-term and accompanying study BESTandermatt fulfills requirements as recommended by the local society in the Sustainability Assessment Plan for Adjustment (Ernst Basler + Partner, 2006). This include for example, the promotion of the participation of all population groups, the development of measures⁹ in close co-operation with the population and monitoring of the development and impact of the tourist resort on the local population. The study shows that it is possible to involve the local population in the development of tourism, even after the completion of formal legal procedures, such as the modification of zoning plans and the planning permission procedures.

Exercise in class:

1. Role of travelers and touring

Discuss in group of 4

- How do students see themselves as "travelling persons"? What are their ideas and expectations? What holiday culture do they cultivate?
- Do students know the role of the person they are visiting? If so, what are their experiences?

2. Opportunities and Threats of tourism for the local population

Based on the article by Marion Thiem (2001), "Tourism and Cultural Identity" and the article by Reinhard Bachleitner (2001). «Alpentourismus: Assessment and Change» potential threats and opportunities of tourism for the local population of the Alpine region of Schoenblick.

⁹ In the case of Andermatt, these are measures in the socioeconomic areas of housing for families and employees as well as dealing with regular residents. For the sociocultural sector, measures were proposed in the areas of communication, children and adolescents, the continuation of the accompanying group, as well as a superordinate measure, a strategy for the development of the Urser valley as an attractive living and living space.

Masters Level:

Reflect on the articles by Thiem and Bachleiter regarding the opportunities and risks described. Link this to the destination Schoenblick. Where do they see the most significant opportunities and risks for the destination? What is the need for action? Formulate some suggestions.

Reading:

Thiem, Marion (2001). Tourismus und kulturelle Identität. In Politik und Zeitgeschichte. B47/2001 S. 27 - 31

Bachleitner, Reinhard (2001). Alpentourismus: Bewertung und Wandel. In Politik und Zeitgeschichte B47/2001 S. 20 – 26.

Chapter 6: Energy use, mobility and climate change

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Module 6: Learning objectives

- Understand the connections between energy sources, CO₂ emissions and climate change problems.
- Understand the energy consumption in a tourist destination (return journey of a guest, mobility on the spot, hotel / buildings).
- Analyse the life cycle of a trip in order to identify environmental impacts and create an eco-balance (in terms of energy).
- Understand energy efficiency measures to improve the ecological balance of travel and destinations.
- Know and understand the concepts of “climate neutrality” and “climate positive”.

6. Module 6: Energy use, CO₂ emissions and climate change

6.1.1. Energy: energy resources and energy use

Contemporary way of life leads to the consumption of huge amounts of energy. But what is energy and what role does energy have in terms of resource consumption and environmental impacts? According to the definition, **energy** is “the ability to perform physical work and thus to cause changes in or to the substance” (Springer Gabler, online). People need energy to generate electricity, for heating, for the production of goods to continue, and energy is always tied to an energy carrier. “**Energy carriers** are natural substances and sources that have a high energy content and are therefore suitable for covering our energy needs” (SFOE, 2014, p. 6).

Renewable energies can be differentiated around non-renewable energies:

- **Non-renewable energy sources** i.e. fossil fuels such as petroleum, natural gas, coal and nuclear fuels were formed by geological transformation processes on dead, organic material. As these processes take millions of years no new fossil fuels can be formed over time-scales relevant to human beings, these are known as non-renewable energies (SFOE, 2012).
- **Renewable energies** include hydropower, wind energy, solar energy, biomass, geothermal energy and ambient heat. These forms of energy occur naturally or continuously in cycles (SFOE, 2014).

Since the 1990s, the final energy consumption per person decreased by 6.1% (FSO, 2014). However, since 1950s the total final energy consumption has increased more than fivefold in Switzerland (see Figure 10). This increase was caused mainly by population growth, an increase in the distance travelled using private motor vehicles, an increase in living space per person, as well as an increase in industrial production and construction activity. Figure 10 illustrates how renewable energies cover around 20% of final energy consumption in Switzerland.

Figure 10: Final energy consumption 1910-2012 by energy carrier

Source: BFS (2014)

Figure 31: Distribution of final energy consumption by consumption group (2013)

Figure 11 pie chart shows that vehicle traffic is the largest energy consumer at 35.4%, followed by households at 28.4%. Similarly, the graph on the left shows that energy consumption in vehicle traffic has risen dramatically over the last 20 years.

Source: BFS (2014)

6.1.2. CO₂-Emissions

If energy is to be derived from fossil fuels (for example, to operate vehicles or to generate electricity), they have to be burnt. During combustion, air pollutants and the greenhouse gas carbon dioxide (CO₂) are emitted, which has an impact on the environment. The emission of greenhouse gases into the atmosphere is referred to as emissions. CO₂ is one of the main causes of man-made climate change. (OECD, 2013a, OEDC, 2013b).

CO₂ footprint is often used as a reference (also called as CO₂ Balance): "The **CO₂ footprint** is a measure of the total amount of carbon dioxide emissions, directly and indirectly, through activity or life stages of a product"(Wiedmann & Minx, 2008, p. 4).

Figure 42: Share of the total greenhouse gas emissions

Source: BAFU (2014a)

6.1.3. CO₂ law and regulation

The basis for Swiss climate policy is the CO₂ Act, which implements the international reduction commitments of the Kyoto Protocol at a national level. In addition to this the law also contains interim targets and measures to reduce greenhouse gas emissions. Whether the prescribed reduction pathways are adhered to is examined using annual surveys. As of 1 January 2013, the revised CO₂ Act was enforced and includes the following objectives (FOEN, 2013):

- Switzerland is to reduce its greenhouse gas emissions by 2020 by at least 20% compared to 1990 levels.
- The law deals primarily with fossil fuels, but also covers other important greenhouse gases in addition to CO₂.
- In addition, the Federal Government has a co-ordinating role in adapting to climate change.

6.1.4. Climate change

Over the last 130 years (1880-2012), the temperature has increased by 0.85 ° C according to world averages. Although the global climate is subject to natural fluctuations, the strong warming since 1970 is no longer only explained by this. The most likely explanation for this warming is due to the increased greenhouse gas emissions caused by human life and work: combustion of fossil fuels, deforestation of the tropical rainforests, etc. As greenhouse gases alter the atmosphere, they causing a warming of the earth's surface and a lower atmosphere arises. (OcCC, 2008; FOEN, 2014b; FOEN, 2010)

Figure 13: Climate indicators: Count of number of summers in spring in Lucerne

Source: Meteoschweiz, 2014

The consequences of this warming are considerable: the rise in air and ocean temperatures and the associated decrease in snow coverage, the melting of glaciers and ice sheets, resulting in an increase in the temperature levels as well as an increase in heat waves, droughts and thunderstorms. (OcCC, 2008; FOEN, 2010).

6.2. Energy, CO₂, climate change and tourism

As an Alpine country, Switzerland is particularly affected by climate change, which has not only an ecological, but also a social and economic impact. For tourism it means people are affected by climate change, whilst they are also a major contributor to it.

Figure 14: Percentage of greenhouse gas emissions in Saint Martin de Belleville (F)

Source: mountain-riders.org in CIPRA, 2011, S. 9

Tourism accounts for about 5% of global CO₂ emissions. Of this, tourist traffic accounted for around 75%, accommodation 21% and local activities 4% (UNWTO / UNEP / WMO, 2008 in CIPRA, 2011).

Figure 15: CO₂ emissions from transport

Source: Federal Environment Agency, 2008

Travel traffic is the largest contributor to greenhouse gas emissions. However, not every means of transport produces the same amount of CO₂ emissions (Figure 15):

Other tourism offers and activities that also have a high level of energy and resource consumption. Some facts:

- Water consumption on holiday: 400 - 600 liters per head and day (average daily consumption: 200 liters)
- A golf course in an Alpine area: an average of 50 million liters of water per year for irrigation
- Snowmaking machines require 200-500 l per m² and winter

Table 13 illustrates the energy consumption and CO₂ emissions of various means of transport or travel routes in Switzerland:

Table 13: Energy consumption and CO₂ emissions of various means of transport and routes

Means of transport	Consumption per person	Energy consumption (in l gasoline)	CO ₂ Emissions (in kg)	Source
Travel by train Lucerne-Engelberg		0.56	0.20	sbb.ch
Travel with the E-Bike Luzern-Engelberg (35km)			0.19	Fairkehr-Magazin
Travel by train Lucerne-Zurich		0.93	0.34	sbb.ch
Travel by car Lucerne-Zurich		5.2	10.4	sbb.ch
Flight Zurich - London (with Swiss)			193	myclimate.org
Flight Zurich - New York (with Swiss)			1'172	myclimate.org
Flight Zurich - Rio de Janeiro (with Swiss)			1'784	myclimate.org

Figure 16 shows an overview of the CO₂-Emissions of different holiday trips (the starting point is a city in Germany).

Figure 16: CO₂-Emissions in various holiday trips

Source: WWF (2009)

Through a voluntary contribution to climate protection, it is possible to compensate for the CO₂ emissions of a trip or a holiday. The implementation is carried out according to the principle of "accounting - reducing - compensating". This means that for a journey all relevant CO₂ emissions are calculated and compensated for by purchasing climate protection certificates from projects. For example, if one contributes 2.5t CO₂ from a flight, one should purchase CO₂ protection certificates equivalent to 2.5t CO₂ (-e) in order to make the trip "climate neutral". It is also possible to buy more climate protection certificates in order not only to carry out the journey "climate neutrally" but also to achieve a positive climate contributions. In Switzerland, the organization Myclimate allows the calculation of emissions both for private persons and households, as well as for companies. On the basis of the determined CO₂ emissions, the amount for compensation is calculated. Myclimate invests the resulting financial resources in environmental projects that use renewable energies, implement energy efficiency measures, reduce methane emissions, reforestation and reforestation initiatives that reduce the pressure on protected forests and "hot spots" of biodiversity. For more information, please visit www.myclimate.org.

6.3. Opportunities and Risks of Climate Change for Alpine Destinations

Climate change is not only a threat to tourism but also opens up interesting opportunities:

Table 24: Opportunities and Risks of Climate Change for Alpine Destinations

Consequences on	Opportunities	Hazards
City tourism	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> increased revitalisation of public spaces during hot summers → attractiveness enhancement through Mediterraneanisation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Increased health-damaging phenomena (ozone, fine dust) due to extreme weather conditions → Attractiveness of cities is decreased
Rural tourism	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Summer: coastal regions profit from tourism when temperatures are warmer 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Winter: rising snowfall limit → lower-Alpine ski resorts are no longer profitable
Alpine Tourism	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Opportunities for mountain tourism through heat periods in the summer → Summer holidays Improved competition for high-altitude areas with snow safety 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Danger to traffic routes (avalanches) → Difficult accessibility / protection and rebuilding measures necessary / higher costs decreasing snow safety and changes in the landscape (eg glacier swelling) influence the attractiveness of tourism areas

Source: Müller & Lehmann Friedli, 2011

6.4. Life Cycle Analysis

Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) is a systematic analysis of environmental impacts over the entire life cycle of a product (from cradle to grave). Calculations of environmental effects during the production, the utilisation phase and the disposal of the product, as well as the related upstream and downstream processes (eg production of the raw materials and supplies), are carried out.

The analysis includes various phases (e.g., a bicycle, a trip or a hotel building) as well as a balance sheet in which inputs and resource consumption (input information) are used for the benefit (functional unit) or the correlated emissions (output variables, outputs) (Figure 16). According to an LCA, it is possible to determine the environmental impacts by means of quantitative indicators (eg the indication of CO₂ emissions, water consumption or waste produced).

An LCA makes it possible to show optimisation potentials in environmental management for different products. For example, the Accor hotel group uses this methodology to calculate the most important environmental impacts of their hotel chain worldwide (Accor, 2011). LCA can also be used to calculate the environmental impact of a trip to a destination (Kuo & Chen, 2009). In order to perform the LCA analysis correctly, a large number of quantitative data of the individual phases of the life of the product are necessary.

Figure 57: Life Cycle Analysis

Sources:

<http://eplca.jrc.ec.europa.eu/>

http://www.kyoceradocumentsolutions.co.uk/index/products/sustainable_design/lifecycle_assessment.html

6.5. Good examples of energy efficiency measures

CO₂ reduction is an important goal of climate policy. Processes such as the use of a fuel or even a human activity that do not affect the carbon dioxide concentration of the atmosphere or whose emissions are compensated are referred to as climate neutral (Energy dictionary, online). In order to get closer to the climate goals, legislation to introduce energy efficiency measures is required.

6.6. Hotels and buildings

Like all other companies, tourist enterprises are subject to the CO₂ tax on fossil fuels (**CO₂ Act / Regulation**). Companies pay about CHF 36 per tonne of CO₂. If the set targets are not reached, the charge can be reduced to max. of CHF 120. Energy expenditures are a substantial cost block in the hotel industry. Hotel operators with an annual output of at least 100 tonnes of CO₂ are exempt from the CO₂ tax. In return, they must undertake to reduce their emissions individually or in groups through concrete measures. The CO₂ regulation controls, among other things, the details of the exemption. (Hotelleriesuisse, 2012).

Table 15 shows some good examples of energy efficiency measures in hotels and other tourist buildings. The listing is not exhaustive.

Table 35: E Energy efficiency measures for hotels

Energy efficiency measures (a selection)	Source
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Central switch in guest rooms, combined with the outside door lock (cuts most power to the room when not occupied electricity) • Purchase of low energy consumption modern household and electronic devices • Use of heat pumps • Building Insulation 	hotelpower.ch
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Insert a motion detector, replace the lamps, check the seals, insert ventilation systems with time switches, and insulate the pipes • Efficient refrigerators • Heat recovery in the dishwasher • Lighting concepts (use of LED, use of daylight etc.) • Plan room layout (Hotel floors with full occupancy) 	Dehoga (Verband für Hotellerie und Gastronomie Deutschland)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • MINERGIE standard for new buildings and extensive conversions • Hot water preparation via solar systems on roofs • In the case of heating sanitation, CO₂-neutral energy forms are converted • Reduction of water consumption thanks to extra valves • Waste heat use for the cooling of own restaurants 	Schweizer Jugendherbergen

6.7. Mobility

On arrival and departure, energy can be saved or used efficiently. Table 16 shows a selection of mobility energy efficiency measures for those responsible at the destination as well as for guests:

Table 46: Energy Efficiency Measures for Mobility

Energy Efficiency Measures for Mobility	Sources
<p><i>Tips for Destinations</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Rental of e-bikes, bicycles, e-scooters etc. with all accessories included • Ensure high availability of major attractions with public transport and low-speed traffic • Continuous foot and bike network with signposting of the most important destinations • Promotion of arrivals and departures outside of particularly busy weekends • Park-and-Ride facilities • Guided hiking and biking tours • Electric taxis • Local bus with regular timetables and Stop on request • Information on baggage transport with the public transport services “door-to-door”, etc. • Arrival and departure with OV at the top level of the site and integration online timetable • Offers of soft mobility at the top the website • Information folders on public transport offers in hotels • 	<p>Solère et al. (2014)</p>
<p><i>Tips for Guests</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Select destinations that are easily accessible by public transport • Arrival, if possible by public transport or coach • If arriving by car, then ensure the car is fully occupied • Activities on the spot by public transport or by slow train (bike, walking, etc.) • Use Park + Rail offers at railway stations, if the place of residence is not optimally developed with the public transport system • Avoid using aircraft when travelling less than 700km • For distances over 700 kilometers, schedule a minimum of eight days stay and a minimum of 15 days' stay for 2,000 kilometers • If CO₂ emissions are unavoidable, compensate for CO₂ emissions 	<p>www.sbb.ch/umwelt www.nachhaltigleben.ch www.wwf.at</p>

Exercise in class:

In the description of the Destination Schoenblick (Case Study Module No. 3), you can see which guests are arriving by which means of transport and how they move around at the destination.

It is recommended that students work in groups of 3 to 4.

1. Calculate the best carbon footprint for your arrival and departure with the help of at least two different CO₂ calculators, which origin market (Germany, China, India, Brazil, Russia). Also note the cost of the possible compensation for each country.
2. Calculate your balance for the last vacation with the aid of different CO₂ calculators. Also note the cost of the possible compensation for the trip.
3. As an expert in tourism and mobility, you are commissioned by the municipal council to present measures to improve the ecological balance of tourism. Provide concrete measures for the arrival and departure of the guests.
4. Consider your next holiday trip. Will you change something in your own behavior? What changes will you implement?
5. Present your results to the whole group. A subsequent discussion with the fellow students will take place.

Reading:

Bundesamt für Umwelt 2014. Leben mit dem Klimawandel Umweltmagazine 0/2014. Seiten 6-32.

Staatsekretariat für Wirtschaft SECO 2014. Schwerpunkt: Klimawandel. Magazine Insight Nr. 4/2014 Seiten 1-8.

Further reading:

Informationen zum Klimawandel: BAFU (2014b). Klimawandel. Online (25.07.2014): <http://www.bafu.admin.ch/klima/00469/index.html?lang=de>

Der Tourismus im Klimawandel: Müller, H. & Weber, F. (2008). 2030: Der Schweizer Tourismus im Klimawandel. Schweiz Tourismus / Forschungsinstitut für Freizeit und Tourismus (FIF) der Universität Bern.

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Further internet sources:

- Bundesamt für Umwelt BAFU: <http://www.bafu.admin.ch/klima/index.html?lang=de>
- WWF Schweiz: <http://www.wwf.ch/de/hintergrundwissen/klima/klimawandel/>
- Neue Zürcher Zeitung: <http://www.nzz.ch/dossiers/wissenschaft/klimawandel-2.17309>

- Bundesamt für Energie BFE: <http://www.bfe.admin.ch/themen/index.html?lang=de>
- Stiftung Energie Schweiz: <http://www.energieschweiz.ch/de-ch/home.aspx>
- DEHOGA Energiekampagne für Hotels und Gaststätten: <http://energiekampagne-gastgewerbe.de/>
- CO2-calculator:
 - https://co2.myclimate.org/de/offset_further_emissions
 - Für die Mobilität in Europa: <http://www.ecopassenger.org/>
 - <http://www.mobitool.ch/typo/tools/>
 - <http://www.novatlantis.ch/2000-watt-gesellschaft/eco2-rechner.html>
 - http://www.sbb.ch/sbb-konzern/ueber-die-sbb/verantwortung-fuer-gesellschaft-und-umwelt/nachhaltige-mobilitaet/umweltvertraegliche-mobilitaet/umweltbilanzierung.marketingurl_%2524%2524%2524umwelt-rechner.html
- Life cycle analysis: EU Plattform: <http://eplca.jrc.ec.europa.eu/>

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Chapter 7: Culture

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7. Module 7: Culture

7.1. Introduction

Module 7: Learning objectives

- Recognise and understand the complex concepts of “culture” and “cultural resources”
- Understand culture as a resource for tourism
- Understand the positive and negative interactions between culture and tourism
- Recognise the most important implementation areas for Swiss tourism
- Become familiar with the Engadin Scuol Samnaun Val Müstair Destination as a good example

7.2. Introduction to the concept of culture

Culture is a factor of the so-called “original offer”, which exists without tourism (for example, language, customs, architecture, etc.), but it is also an appealing tourist attraction. In addition, culture is also an integral part of the “off-the-shelf” tourism offer, which include the services and facilities that are specific to tourism such as festivals and museums (Müller, 2008, p. 135.).

Therefore, culture is an important basis for and part of tourism. Culture corresponds to a resource or a capital and as a result enables a destination to be positioned on the market. Therefore, cultural resources represent a location advantage and play a decisive role in building competitiveness (Keller, 2000, p. 25; Ooi, 2002, p. 91 in: Siller, 2010, p. 97). Cultural heritage is regarded as an irreplaceable and finite resource (Bendixen, 2006, p. 327).

Whilst the term culture used to refer primarily to high culture (i.e. historical works of art, paintings, music, architecture, etc.), conceptually it currently also includes everyday objects and behaviours (Crepaz & Hrovat-Forstinger, 1999, p. 28). According to the UNESCO definition “culture can be viewed in its widest sense as the totality of the unique intellectual, material, intellectual and emotional aspects that characterise a society or a social group. This includes not only art and literature, but also life forms, the fundamental rights of man, value systems, traditions and faiths” (UNESCO, 1983).

Cultural resources can be subdivided broadly into tangible and intangible types. UNESCO (1972) distinguishes three groups of **material cultural heritage** (for example castles, churches, modern architecture) with an extraordinary universal value:

- *Monuments* are works of architecture, large sculptures and monumental paintings, objects or remains of an archaeological nature, inscriptions, caves

- *Ensembles* are groups of individuals or interconnected buildings
- *Sites* are works by the human hand or joint works of nature and man, as well as archaeological sites

Intangible cultural heritage is a living tradition that has been handed down over generations. UNESCO (2003) distinguishes five areas where the intangible heritage is recognised:

- Verbal traditions and expressions, including language as the bearer of the immaterial cultural heritage (for example: legends, fairy tales, regional dialects)
- Performing arts (for example: singing, dancing, folk theater)
- Social practices, rituals and festivals (e.g. particular customs, processions, traditional ways of life)
- Knowledge and practices in dealing with nature and the universe (e.g., knowledge about medicinal plants or agriculture)
- Expertise in traditional crafting techniques (e.g. wood processing, cheese making, painting)

The practices and symbols of these traditions shape the appearance of a tourist destination, a region or a country. Beyond cultural heritage, culture encompasses current artistic and cultural productions (e.g. festivals, art exhibition previews, theatre performances, concerts).

7.3. Cultural Inventories

Inventories are an opportunity to capture cultural resources independently of tourism. Inventories can be created at the local, cantonal, national or international level. They can serve as an active or passive basis for tourism. On the one hand, they serve to protect and preserve the cultural heritage; and on the other, the elements contained within the inventory can also be actively promoted in the tourism offer. In particular, the cultural heritage listing by UNESCO on the “World Heritage Sites” list has a immense tourism potential. Such recognition can be used for marketing, as the UNESCO label is viewed by visitors as a quality seal of approval. Selected inventories are briefly explained in Table 17.

Table 17: Protected Areas in Switzerland

Inventory name	Cultural resources	Number of elements	Website
UNESCO world heritage	Natural and cultural objects	Worldwide over 980 localities, 11 of them in Switzerland	www.unesco.ch www.unesco-destination-schweiz.ch
Federal Inventory of Switzerland's Protected Sites of National Importance (ISOS)	Location: e.g. Medieval towns, farmers' villages, hamlets, quarters, industrial sites, cultural landscapes	More than 1,280 properties	www.bak.admin.ch/isos
List of living traditions in Switzerland	Immaterial Cultural Heritage (Living Traditions)	167 traditions	www.lebendige-traditionen.ch
Culinary heritage of Switzerland	Food	Approximately 400 products	www.kulinarischeserbe.ch
Swiss cableway	Cable cars, cable cars, ski lifts	129 objects	www.seilbahninventar.ch
Federal Inventory of the Historic Traffic Routes of Switzerland	Paths, roads, waterways		www.ivs.admin.ch

7.3.1. Federal Inventory of the Protected Sites of Switzerland of National Importance (ISOS)

The aim of the ISOS is to preserve the qualities that lead to a designated locality's appearance retaining national value and to prevent irreversible damage to this from occurring. Romantic medieval towns are not the only noteworthy locations in Switzerland, there are villages, factories and extensive cultivated landscapes. As a rule, individual buildings are not inventoried, but places are inventoried. The ISOS currently comprises more than 1,280 properties. (BAK, 2013a)

7.3.2. UNESCO-World heritage

UNESCO has set itself the task of preserving the cultural and natural resources of the world, which have an exceptional universal value. In 1975, Switzerland was one of the first states to ratify the associated convention. As a result, Switzerland undertook to preserve, cultivate and provide access to outstanding cultural and natural entities on its territory. Currently the Welterbeliste comprises over 980 sites, 11 of which are in Switzerland (BAK, 2013c).

Presently, the following sites come under the domain of cultural heritage in Switzerland:

- Bern Oldtown
- Stiftsbezirk St. Gallen
- Benedictine Monastery of St. John in Müstair
- Castles and the fortifications of Bellinzona
- Cultural heritage Lavaux wine region
- Rhaetian railway in the Albula / Bernina landscape
- La Chaux-de-Fonds / Le Locle, city landscape and watch industry
- Prehistoric pile dwelling around the Alps

Presently, the following sites come under the domain of natural heritage in Switzerland:

- Schweizer Alpen Jungfrau-Aletsch
- Monte San Giorgio
- Schweizer Tektonikarena Sardona

Whilst the Swiss Commission for UNESCO (SUC) is responsible for institutional relations at an international level, it is the Swiss Federal Department of Foreign Affairs (FDFA) that is the co-ordinating body that advises the Confederation about its dealings with UNESCO, the association "UNESCO Destination Schweiz", the development of offers, marketing / communication and the establishment of networks between the Swiss UNESCO World Heritage sites and UNESCO biosphere.

7.3.3. List of living traditions in Switzerland

As a result of the ratification of the UNESCO Convention on the Conservation of Intangible Cultural Heritage on 16 October 2008, Switzerland has undertaken to develop, maintain and periodically update an inventory of intangible cultural heritage in Switzerland. The "List of Living Traditions in Switzerland" is a comprehensive documentation of the intangible cultural heritage of Switzerland and is available at www.lebendige-traditionen.ch. The national list currently includes 167 traditions, which are assigned to five categories (Table 1). It contributes to raising awareness amongst the public, promoting the recognition of the bearers of living traditions, supporting, promoting the practice and communication of living traditions (BAK, 2012; BAK, 2013d).

As a complement to the "List of Living Traditions in Switzerland", the Inventory "Kulina-rerige der Schweiz" is a collection of around 400 traditional Swiss culinary products, their production, characteristics and history (BAK, 2012). Examples of other inventories include the Swiss Cableway

Inventory, (ropeways are considered to be technical monuments) (BAK, 2013b) and the Federal Inventory of the Historic Traffic Routes of Switzerland (IVS) (ASTRA, 2014).

Table 18 overview of possible interactions between culture and tourism.

Interaction	Affected sustainability dimensions		
	Social	En-viron-mental	Econo-mical
Increasing awareness of one's own identity: In times of globalisation (through an appreciative view from the outside) the analysis of one's own local values and traditions can strengthen one's identity and promote cohesion in society.	X		
Intercultural exchange: The exploration of foreign cultures - especially personal contact - leads to increased mutual understanding and acceptance. Stereotypes / prejudices can be broken down.	X		
Preserving and promoting the cultural resource: Revenue from tourism can be used to conserve cultural resources (for example, for structural measures / renovations). The interest and the appreciation outsiders, as well as the possibility to show traditions to an audience is an incentive to continue traditions.	X	(X)	X
Basis for tourist offers: The cultural resources are an important basis for initiating tourist offers, in order that guests needs are satisfied and valuable jobs created.			X
Attractiveness: Culture can strengthen the attractiveness and competitiveness of localities, regions and countries - not only in terms of tourism, but also in terms of the quality of living and the location.	X		X
The basis for marketing a destination: Cultural resources are beneficial to a location and their unique nature enables them to be used to differentiate between other destinations and this can be communicated to foreign visitors.			X
Crowding effects: Mass tourism, in particular, can cause crowds to form (e.g. large numbers of visitors and locals at a locality can cause excessive wear, high flow rates etc.) and lead overcrowding / impairment of cultural resources as well as the environment.	X	X	
Accommodation / destruction of the cultural resource: Cultural resources can be physically affected by overuse, inappropriate handling, vandalism, etc. In addition cultural heritage runs the risk of changing as a result of adaptation to mass tourist needs. Instead of strengthening identity, local societies can become alienated if for example, the intangible cultural heritage is only listed by foreigners (i.e. non-practitioners) for tourists.	X		X

7.4. Main fields of activity in cultural tourism

Forster et al. (2007) have identified the following fields of action for culture and tourism in their analysis:

- *Experience deficit:* Many cultural attractions are available but not visible to visitors.
- *Innovations deficit:* Clear strategic positions, contacts, professional knowledge and people are often missing in the process of further innovative development of offers.
- *Sensitivity deficit:* The lack of sensitivity of the local population to their own cultural values.

- *Knowledge access deficit*: Knowledge of cultural institutions / available actors often barely accessible, incomprehensible or not yet prepared for tourism.
- *Value deficit*: Small structures with numerous actors leads to a separation and fragmentation of the offers and a lack of transparency regarding the quantity, which in turn leads to a low value added to the economy.
- *Quality deficit*: The expectations of the guests can not be fulfilled due to a wide and improvised service chain.
- *Network and co-ordination deficit*: Lack of exchange of experience between actors and inadequate coordination.

7.5. Good example: Destination Engadin Scuol Samnaun Val Müstair

The destination consists of the three regions Samnaun, Scuol and Val Müstair. It is managed by the Destination Management Organization “Tourism Engadin Scuol Samnaun Val Müstair” (TESSVM). The destination is positioned as the nature and cultural holiday region providing the most attractive multi-generational offer in Switzerland. The focus is on experiencing the whole natural and cultural attractions. Here nature and landscape are to be preserved and nurtured. The vibrant authentic culture is promoted. Locals and guests/visitors are able to meet because of the inclusion of the local population in cultural and natural attractions (TESSVM, online (a)).

Figure 18: The geographical location of destination Engadin Scuol Samnaun Val Müstair

Source: TESSVM, online (b)

Figure 69: A map of Engadin Scuol Samnaun Val Müstair

Source: Samnaun Val Müstair

In 2011, the Destination Engadin Scuol Samnaun Val Müstair was awarded the environmental prize of MILESTONE as a “model region for sustainability”, as many projects and areas of supply development are aimed at sustainability (TESSVM, online (a)). Figure 20-25 provide a selection of available cultural resources:

Figure 20: Kloster St. Johann in Müstair

Source: Foundation Pro Kloster

Material Cultural heritage:

In addition to being a UNESCO biosphere and a Swiss national park, Val Müstair, has a great cultural treasure. The monastery of St. Johann in Müstair is a UNESCO World Heritage site, a special internationally known attraction.

Figure 71: Schloss Tarasp

Source: Schloss Tarasp

Tarasp Castle, which is of national appeal, offers guided tours to visitors and can be used for special and private events (banquets, weddings, etc.). In the Silvretta area you can experience history and archeology as part of hiking tours.

Figure 82: Engadiner Houses in Guarda

Source: Pro Guarda

Architecture

The architecture of Engadin houses is noteworthy. The village of Guarda, registered in the ISOS is one of the most impressive sites. It has particularly beautiful Engadin houses including the most characteristic and best preserved.

Figure 93: Guarda

Source: Giovanni Danielli

In 1975 the village Guarda received the Wakker prize from the Swiss Homeland Security. The Wakker Prize is awarded to municipalities, which are able to show special achievements with regard to the development of the town and the settlement (www.wakkerpreis.ch).

Immaterial cultural heritage / Living traditions:

The intangible cultural heritage and craftsmanship of “sgraffito painting” also plays a role in the architecture of the Engadin houses. A typical element of the houses, the artistic sgraffito decorations, are carved from the plaster.

The Sgraffito houses are a main feature in the children's book “Schellen-Ursli”. The book made the custom of Chalandamarz widely known and inspired the implementation of the "Schellenursliweg in Guarda".

Figure 10: Chalandamarz

Source: TESSVM

On the morning of the first of March (the beginning of the year in the Roman Empire, prior to the Julian calendar) all the school children proceed through the streets and alleys of the villages and celebrating Chalandamarz. Spring, is announced with singing, whipping and bell ringing, thus marking the end of the cold, dark Winter.

The intangible cultural heritage also includes the Romansh language, which is spoken, cultivated and maintained in the Unterengadin and Val Müstair. Romansh is an integral part of the regional culture. It is not only the language of songs and books, but also the language spoken in the streets, in shops and in the schools. In the Val Müstair region, there are language-learning trips during which visitors converse with local people and in Ftan near Scuol, a local person accompanies the visitors on the “Monday evening rumantsch”.

Figure 115: Hom Strom

Source: Graubünden Ferien

Other traditions include, “Hom Strom” (man of straw) in Scuol or the Erntedankfest (harvest festival) in Val Müstair. On the first day of the feast of Hom Strom, schoolchildren intertwine thick strands of threshed rye straw, around a 9 metre high pole creating a Strohmann (a straw man), which is then set alight as a sacrificial ritual heralding the coming of summer.

One of the most famous culinary legacies of the Canton of Graubünden is probably the “Bündner Nusstorte”, which is taken home by many tourists as an edible souvenir.

7.6. Culture management

The Center for Contemporary Art NAIRS in Scuol is an example of contemporary culture. It focuses on the cultural self-understanding of today's Engadine and conducts events about the cultural life of the Rumantscha.

7.7. Positive co-operation at the destination is required for the usage of cultural resources in tourism

- Sustainable development in tourism is the guiding principle / aim of the Destination Management Organisation TESSVM
- Good networking within the destination through TESSVM (personal contacts, participation in commissions, etc.)
- Ensure a position at the tourism organization for the development of services
- Communication / marketing of cultural offers (offered by cultural operators)
- Collaboration with universities of applied sciences
- Collaboration with cultural stakeholders and institutions (for example, the creation of local brochures in co-operation with local historians, tips for cultural campaigners regarding their offer, provision of communication tools)
- Co-operation with interested authorities and associations
- Public invitation for tenders to access cultural offers within the framework of the “vacation tips”¹⁰
- Co-operation with the cantonal cultural office (but only for the financing of cultural projects and the provision of contacts)
- Strong cantonal, cultural promotion laws
- Technical and visitor regulating measures for the protection of cultural objects (e.g. at the Mon Müstair monastery)

Table 19: Actors

Actor	Function	Website
Tourism Engadin Scuol Samnaun Val Müstair	Offer design and marketing	www.engadin.com
Cultural, historical, etc.	Archiving / documentation of cultural goods, information procurement and processing, provision of guided tours	
Cultural institutions, e.g. Museums, festivals, Mon Müstair monastery, NAIRS Center for Contemporary Art	Providing access to culture, archiving / documentation, etc. of cultural goods and the design and marketing of offers	www.museenland-gr.ch www.nairs.ch www.muestair.ch
Associations / foundations / umbrella organizations such as Pro Rätia, Pro Helvetia, Lia Rumantscha	Promotion of cultural creativity and its facilitation. Financial support for cultural projects, creation of information and promotion material and its own programmes	www.pro-raetia.ch www.prohelvetia.ch www.liarumantscha.ch

¹⁰ In brochures as well as online, possibilities / activities are presented, in order to discover and experience the Unterengadin.

Office for Cultural Graubünden: cultural promotion, monument care, archaeological services, etc.	Promotion and facilitation of cultural creativity, research and preservation of cultural objects and financial support for cultural projects	www.afk.gr.ch
Tourism and Sustainable Development at the Zurich University of Applied Sciences	Research and advice on natural and cultural tourism (e.g. offering bots)	www.wergenstein-tourismus.ch
Institute for Cultural Research	Implementation and promotion of cultural research (in particular with regard to the AI-Penraum, Graubünden and its neighboring regions)	www.kulturforschung.ch

Classroom exercises:

As you have read in the introduction to Destination Schoenblick, a Chinese investor is planning a 4-star-plus resort, which is aimed specifically at guests from the emerging distant markets of Brazil, Russia, India and China. Now, we would like you to show the local community what cultural offerings will be recommended to these new visitors and how both sides - local people and tourists can benefit from this.

Make groups and sketch (on a flipchart) an idea for a possible tourist offer in the area of culture. Answer the following questions:

- What cultural property is recommended in the tourist offer?
- What are the contents / elements of the offer?
- What does the offer comprise (an event, a course, an excursion, a theme trail, a museum etc.).
- How long does the offer last? How often is it offered (once or several times a year)?
- To which target group is the offer addressed?
- How much does the offer cost?
- How much are the development costs?
- Which actors are involved in the development of the offer?
- How achievable is a real exchange / encounter between tourists and locals?
- What dangers / challenges could arise from the use of the appropriate culture? How could this be countered?
- How can the offer be designed so that the local population also benefits from it?

Remember to pay attention to the three dimensions of sustainability!

Potential additional task:

- Creation of a one-way flyer to market the offer.

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Futher internet resources:

- | | |
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| www.afk.gr.ch | www.muestair.ch |
| www.bak.admin.ch/isos | www.nairs.ch |
| www.bak.admin.ch/kulturerbe | www.prohelvetia.ch |
| www.engadin.com | www.pro-raetia.ch |
| www.ivs.admin.ch | www.seilbahninventar.ch |
| www.kulinarischeserbe.ch | www.unesco.ch/wie/kultur |
| www.lebendige-traditionen.ch | www.unesco-destination-schweiz.ch |
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Chapter 8: Landscape

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8. Module 8: Landscape

8.1. Introduction

Module 8: Learning Objectives

- Recognise and understand the definitions of landscape, the different types of landscapes, landscape changes, landscape assessments, as well as the influence of second homes.
- Recognise, understand, and evaluate the impact of settlements and tourist activities on different landscapes.
- Recognise, understand and judge a case study in the Swiss Alpine Space: recognise suitable implementation options for the development and protection of landscapes, including second homes.

8.2. Introduction to the landscape concept

If you open your eyes, every day becomes an experience. *Oskar Kokoschka (1886-1980)*

There are various definitions of landscape. The Swiss Federal Office for the Environment **FOEN** (2008) defines landscape as follows:

“Landscapes spatially form the lived and experienced environment of man, which as an individuum (indivisible entity) as well as the society enables him to fulfil physical and psychological needs. Landscapes as a resource have diverse functions. They are a habitat for humans, animals and plants, a diverse recreational and identification space as well as a spatial expression of the cultural heritage. They also contribute to the added value. Landscapes are dynamic, formed with natural features such as rocks, soil, water, air, light, fauna and flora in interaction with human use and design.”

Figure 126: Nature and Cultural landscapes meet in Saas-Fee Valais Canton

Source: Giovanni Danielli

Figure 14: Highest Moorland in Europe on the Göschenentalp UR

Source: Giovanni Danielli

Landscapes are created by the interaction between nature and humans, and fulfil important functions for every individual and society as a whole: economically as a location factor, ecologically as a natural resource and socially as a living and recreation area. In landscapes, natural and cultural developments are important.

Figure 15: Landscape Bietschhorn in Lötschental VS

Source: Giovanni Danielli

Natural landscapes are parts of the landscape, which are largely original and are not visibly influenced by humans. In Switzerland, they are found only in the high mountains or in individual nature reserves.

Figure 169: Natural landscape in the Alpstein AI

Source: Giovanni Danielli

In **nature-oriented landscapes**, interference by man is minimal. Intensive use of the landscape has caused natural regions to shrink considerably and they have often become isolated.

Landscapes are experienced differently and emotionally. The nature of a landscape is determined by natural and human influences.

Figure 30: A traditional cultural landscape (historical cultural landscapes) near Feld im Binntal in Canton Valais

Source: Giovanni Danielli

Traditional cultural landscapes still show their landscape and a great variety of types. Since there is little fertilization, the nutrient richness is low. An example of a traditional cultural landscape is an alp.

Figure 171: An intensively used landscape near the city (Wetzikon, Zurich)

Source: Giovanni Danielli

Highly cultivated landscapes have nutrient rich soils as a result of intensive fertilizer use to promote distinctive grasses. Biodiversity in such landscapes is rather low.

Figure 32: A city landscape in Zurich

Source: Giovanni Danielli

Urban landscapes are for the most part artificial landscapes, but may contain interesting ecosystems with a medium to high biodiversity.

8.3. Impact of tourism on natural landscapes

The landscape is the most important element of tourism (Müller, 2003, p. 89). The quality of a landscape is a crucial influencing factor for many tourists when deciding to visit a particular place. Landscapes can be used both as recreation areas and as bases for sporting activities. It is beneficial for visitors to see beautiful landscapes. The recreational function of a landscape is based on the attractiveness gradient between the group landscapes and the target areas.

Figure 183: The impact of tourism activities on the landscape

8.4. Landscape and second homes

Whilst second homes do contribute to changing a landscape they also represent a tourist potential, although their construction does threaten sensitive landscapes and settlement areas. In the Swiss Alps there are about 300,000 second homes, which corresponds to about 26% of all apartments in the country.

Figure 194: Map of the municipalities showing the proportion of apartments occupancy rates higher than 20%

Source: ARE 2012

However, in some cantons and municipalities the percentages are much higher. In Grisons (Canton Graubünden) it is about 37%, in Laax even more than 80%. Figure 33 shows that the vast majority of second homes are located in the Alps and near lakes.

Figure 35: Impact of second home construction

Source: Vereinigung für Landesplanung in Müller (2007, p. 15)

The problematic nature of the second home constructions is primarily related to the fact that, in addition to the long-term dangers, it produces a large number of short-term winners. These are visible when looking at the value chain linked with second home construction. A comprehensive strategy to solve the problems caused by second homes must go beyond restricting the construction of new buildings and also ensure a value-added for the locals, a financing of the community tasks as well as sufficient living space for the locals. Figure 35 shows possible strategies and measures for a sustainable second home policy.

Figure 206: Strategies and measures for a sustainable second home policy

1. Value creation for local residents	2. Financing the municipality's services	3. Increase occupancy	4. Active first home policies
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Second home rentals - Room rentals - Services for lessor - Hybrid models 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Second home taxes - Cost allocation tax - Reinvestment into tourism - Tourist tax 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Information and sensibilisation - Services for lessors - Professional distribution - Financial incentive to rent out second home 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Building zones for locals - Land acquisition by the municipality - Land transfer to cooperatives - Only residents can build second homes

Source: Sonderegger, 2013

8.5. Parks as places for nature protection, tourism and sustainable landscape use

Protected areas are an important basis for ecotourism, nature tourism and nature-oriented tourism, as they provide the most important motive for nature-oriented tourists to visit.

In Switzerland, **three categories** of parks are distinguished:

Nationalpark (NP)

- The main goal of a national park is the unrestricted development of nature.
- The national park has a core and an environmental zone.
- The core zone covers at least 100 km² in the Alps, 75 km² in the Jura. The surrounding zone is a maximum of 1.5 times the core zone.
- The core zone is free of all human intervention.
- The surrounding area also includes small settlements and adapted infrastructure facilities. The focus here is on the sustainable use of natural resources.

Nature- adventure park (NEP)

- These are areas near densely populated settlements.
- The core zone of the NEP covers at least 4 km², the surrounding zone 2 km².
- The NEP must be well-connected to the public transport system and must contain an education centre.
- The population can experience the nature and dynamism of the ecosystems. The NEP contributes to the sensitization of the population to the aspects of nature and the environment.

Regional Naturepark (RNP)

- An RNP covers at least 100 km². It has no core zone.
- The area is intended to include natural and landscape values as well as settlements.

Figure 37 Existing parks and park candidates

Source: BAFU (online)

8.6. Example Guarda GR: Preserving the cultural landscape with spatial planning measures

Figure 38:
The compact Engadine village of Guarda on a unique slope in a traditional cultural landscape.

Guarda is one of the most compact settlements on the southern slope of the Lower Engadine Region. It is classified of national importance in the inventory of Swiss protected areas (ISOS).

Source: Giovanni Danielli

The application of very strict zone planning to modestly sized buildings that could potentially be expanded is outstanding. This means that the compact form of the village can be preserved. A strict building law and a limitation on the number of second apartments has led to the aesthetic development of this location.

Below the village a light agricultural zone and a landscape protection zone exist with a strict construction ban. The landscape protection zone serves to keep the slopes free, thus protecting and preserving the townscape. Agricultural buildings can only be erected at defined sites on the edge of the building zone. The yellow area above the village is a ski area. The village of Guarda remains attractive with such planning measures for tourists looking for authentic locations.

Figure 39: Zone plan of the municipality Guarda.

Source: Canton GR, online

Thanks to its exemplary spatial planning, the village has retained its high spatial qualities and is therefore ideally suited to natural tourism. There are no significant problems with regard to second homes in Guarda, as the village has hardly grown due to strict spatial planning and is of great importance as a first-time residence. The second-occupancy rate is well below 30%.

Exercise in Class

Read the documents provided (about 1 hour)

Bachelor-Level

Part 1) approx. 45 minutes in groups (typically 3 to 4 persons per group)

Group members are to answer the following questions based on the set reading:

1. What are the advantages and disadvantages of second homes?
2. As described in the destination module, a tourist resort is being built in Schoenblick.
3. Where could the optimal location (from a spatial planning point of view) be for this resort?
4. What other conditions need consideration in the planning and construction?
5. How should we avoid the existing second homes in the village?

Part 2) Students will present their results to the whole group.

Part 3) The lecturer will provide critical feedback and replies to the whole group to ensure that all three dimensions of sustainability are covered.

(Parts 2 & 3 45 minutes in total)

Lecture reading:

Landschaften als Grundlage für den Tourismus; in: Danielli G. & Sonderegger R. (2009): Naturtourismus. Rüegger Verlag. Zürich. S. 39 – 46

Kapitel Zweitwohnungen; in: Danielli G. & Sonderegger R. (2014): Raumplanung in der Schweiz. Rüegger Verlag. Zürich. S. 136 – 142

Further internet resources:

Landschaft, Bundesamt für Umwelt: <http://www.bafu.admin.ch/landschaft/index.html?lang=de>

Pärke, Bundesamt für Umwelt: <http://www.bafu.admin.ch/paerke/index.html?lang=de>; <http://www.paerke.ch/>

Zweitwohnungen; Bundesamt für Raumentwicklung. <http://www.are.admin.ch/themen/raumplanung/00236/04094/index.html?lang=de>

Bibliography (Theoretical part)

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Krippendorf J.& Müller H. (1986): Alpsegen Alptraum. Für eine Tourismus-Entwicklung im Einklang mit Mensch und Natur. Kümmerly + Frey. Geographischer Verlag. Bern.

Müller, H. (2011). Tourismuspolitik. Wege zu einer nachhaltigen Entwicklung. Glarus/Chur: Rüegger.

Sonderegger R. (2013): Zweitwohnungen im Alpenraum. Dissertation. Erlangen.

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